

ZAMONAVIY ERKIN KURASHDA RIVOJLANISH AN’ANALARI

Solaydinov Elmurod Shoroidinovich

Andijon davlat universiteti

Sport faoliyati turlari nazariyasi va metodikasi kafedrası

elmurodshoroidinovich87@gmail.com

Annotatsiya: Sport yakkakurashlarini rivojlanishini zamonaviy an’analari erkin kurash bo’yicha yetakchi nazariyachilar tomonidan ishlab chiqilgan. UWW (Birlashgan kurash dunyosi) rahbarlarini sa’y-harakatlari tufayli 2013 yili musobaqalar qoidalariga prinsipial o’zgarishlar kiritildi, kurashchilarning musobaqa faoliyati faollashdi va tomoshabop bo’ldi.

Kalit soʻzlar: Sport, jismoniy sifatlar, harakat, yakkakurash, Birlashgan kurash dunyosi.

ТЕНДЕНЦИИ РАЗВИТИЯ В СОВРЕМЕННОЙ ВОЛЬНОЙ БОРЬБЕ

Солайдинов Эльмурод Шороидинович

Кафедра теории и методики спортивной деятельности

Андижанского государственного университета

E-mail: elmurodshoroidinovich87@gmail.com

Аннотация: Современные тенденции развития спортивных единоборств разработаны ведущими теоретиками по вольной борьбе. В дальнейшем благодаря энергичной деятельности руководителей UWW (Объединенный мир борьбы) внесены принципиальные изменения правил соревнований в 2013 году соревновательная деятельность борцов активизировалась и стала зрелищной. Однако проведение соревнований по новым правилам требовала от борцов значительных усилий не только физических, но и психологических напряжений,

но что в конечном итоге приводит к истощению сил, исчерпанию резервных возможностей.

Ключевые слова: Спорт, физические качества, боевые действия, боевые искусства, United Wrestling World.

DEVELOPMENT TRADITIONS IN MODERN FREESTYLE WRESTLING

Solaydinov Elmurod Shoroidinovich

Department of theory and methodology of sports activities

Andijan state university

E-mail: elmurodshoroidinovich87@gmail.com

Annotation: The modern traditions of the development of martial arts were developed by the leading theorists of freestyle wrestling. Thanks to the efforts of the leaders of the UWW (United World Wrestling), in 2013, fundamental changes were made to the rules of the competitions, the activities of the wrestlers became more active and the audience became more active.

Keywords: Sports, Physical Qualities, Action, Martial Arts, United Wrestling World.

The field of sports science has been established for over 100 years. However, three fundamental questions arise. The author’s article [109; pp. 48–51, 110; pp. 5–6] analyzes the state of modern sports science and raises the following issues: How accurately does it reflect its subject—physical education and sports? Are the primary aspects of this reflection clear and reliable? [110; pp. 5–6]. Historically, (in the 20th century), multiple principal models of sport have been established worldwide, based on different types as well as religious, economic, social, and political foundations. In particular, most scientists in our country have studied the amateur sports model and, similarly, the Olympic model.

The question of the reliability of scientific sports theories has almost been resolved, replaced by the reliability of changes observed in numerous studies of local objects [110; pp. 5–6]. The presented experiences and partial scientific induction from these theoretical frameworks offer incomplete knowledge, limited by the representativeness of the research programs chosen. In our view, only hypothetical-deductive theories, with idealization and interpretation methods, provide reliable knowledge, though such theories are yet to be recognized in sports science [72; pp. 14–16].

Efforts have been made to understand the “qualities” of an individual as a subject of physical education activity and to determine a methodological approach to their structure. In recent years, scientific and methodological literature has shifted from “physical qualities” to “physical (motor) abilities.” We believe the long-dominant term “physical qualities” does not fully represent the field of physical education, despite its inclusion in the curriculum for physical education institutions in 1979.

This raises a question: can the concept of “physical (motor) abilities” be considered a foundational term in general physical education theory? Likely not. Analyzing the subject and individual components of physical education shows that its foundation is physical development achieved through physical means. When considering physical education as a system of interconnected components, physical exercise becomes a crucial factor in the development of an individual’s physical and mental capacities [75; p. 719].

Foreign authors propose an alternative classification of qualities associated with motor activity, focusing on interaction with the environment, physiological and environmental connections, subject-object relationships in activity, and the individual-society relationship. Based on the structural system of voluntary motor actions, they suggest classifying qualities into information-orientation, motivational-directional, and energy-conditioning categories. According to the authors [72; pp. 14–16], this qualities concept represents physical activity hierarchies as separate aspects, making it promising for addressing the problem studied in the article. Detailing key processes

and qualities within physical education allows for specifying the types that play a decisive role.

Thus, it is necessary to consider psychophysical qualities as the initial, broad concept in general physical education theory. Through a systematic approach, qualities should be viewed at different levels as a “multi-layered” phenomenon within physical education activities, with a material basis of various organs and systems [72; pp. 14–16].

Modern traditions in wrestling development have been explored by leading theorists of freestyle wrestling [109; pp. 48–51, 111; p. 99, 134; p. 162, 6; pp. 471–479, 15; pp. 32–34, 61; pp. 45–47, 95; pp. 42–46, 130; p. 18, 18; pp. 89–93], including the influence of body components on high-level wrestlers' preparation. Research findings provide new insights into the evolution of sports wrestling within the International Olympic movement, revealing discrepancies between existing competition rules and prior theoretical standards. Concerns about removing freestyle and Greco-Roman wrestling from the future Olympic program led to the regulation changes, affecting competition and judging systems. Subsequently, significant rule changes were implemented by UWW in 2013, increasing wrestling activity and spectator appeal. However, new rules have heightened both physical and psychological demands, potentially leading to a loss of strength and reserves.

Leading researchers in Uzbekistan have developed contemporary approaches to the theory and methodology of various wrestling types [26; p. 220, 64; p. 137, 7; p. 245, 16; p. 56, 17; pp. 24–26, 83; p. 216, 103; p. 863]. Increasing competition and the equalizing skill level of leading wrestlers globally have resulted in unexpected losses in international arenas and a decline in consistent results for high-level athletes. These trends demand further improvement in training and competition systems for wrestlers, emphasizing technical-tactical skill enhancement, analysis of individual performance, and alignment with modern Olympic traditions [112; p. 600, 18; pp. 89–93, 19; p. 51, 130; p. 18].

The level of athletic achievement closely correlates with a set of individual capacities, including physical qualities and psychological characteristics, which align with the specific demands of particular sports specializations. The principle of individualization in sports preparation systems holds great importance [138; pp. 53–62, 147; p. 50, 153; p. 44].

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